

Sustainable Erasmus+ Travel

Policy recommendations for greener Erasmus+ mobility

Author:

Salome Dermati, Policy and Research Officer, European University Foundation

29/05/2026

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Education and Culture Executive Agency (EACEA). Neither the European Union nor EACEA can be held responsible for them.

Project number	101133927
Project name	Sustainable Erasmus+ Travel
Project acronym	SET
Call	ERASMUS-2023-PCOOP-ENGO
Topic	ERASMUS-EDU-2023-PCOOP-ENGO
Project starting date	01/02/2024
Project duration	28 months
Grant Agreement	GAP-101133927

Deliverable details

Work Package number	5
Deliverable number	2
Deliverable name	Policy recommendations for greener Erasmus+ mobility
Lead Beneficiary	EUF
Author	Salome Dermati
Due date (month)	28
Actual submission	29/05/2026
Type of Deliverable	Public

Revision history

Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
0.1	08/05/2026	Salome Dermati and Maria Ardanova (EUFP)	First draft.
0.2	27/05/2026	Salome Dermati (EUFP)	Updated version with partners' feedback.
0.3	29/05/2026	Salome Dermati (EUFP)	Final version.

Table of contents

Executive summary	3
Key project achievements	4
Introduction	6
Recommendations for green travel	8
Recommendations for green competencies	12
Transversal recommendations	14
A call for better-connected rail infrastructure	16
Conclusions	19
References	20
Annex	22

Abbreviations

CU	Charles University
EACEA	European Education and Culture Executive Agency
ECHE	Erasmus Charter for Higher Education
ESN	Erasmus Student Network
EUUF	European University Foundation
HEI	Higher Education Institution
IRO	International Relations Office/Officer
SET	Sustainable Erasmus+ Travel (project)
U.Porto	University of Porto
UZH	University of Zurich

Executive summary

Key recommendations for greener Erasmus+ student mobility:

1. Recognising the transversal competencies fostered through green travel.

We recommend reframing how programme participants view their sustainable travel experience: as a learning experience that should be championed and therefore be seen as an integral part of their mobility. Beyond the environmental benefits, it is an opportunity to strengthen a wide range of complementary competencies and gain full ownership of them, matching environmental awareness with action. Universities and policymakers should consider how to support the validation and recognition of these competencies.

2. Making green travel the default option.

We recommend positioning green travel as the most inclusive and accessible means of transportation for students and collectively addressing its biggest barriers: price, complexity, and availability. A major step in this direction is to modernise and improve the interconnectedness of long-distance, cross-border train infrastructure in Europe, in negotiation with national rail operators. The recent Passenger Package is a promising legislative tool towards this direction.

3. Upgrading the Erasmus Charter for Higher Education and the Erasmus+ Student Charter.

We recommend strengthening the universities' actionable commitments to environmental sustainability by explicitly mentioning and promoting green travel in the next ECHE. We also propose including the recognition of green travel and green competencies as an entitlement after the mobility period in the Erasmus+ Student Charter to further shift the narrative around the benefits of mobility and encourage students to adopt responsible behaviours.

Key project achievements

TITLE	TYPE	DATE	DESCRIPTION	Link
10 Factsheets and a modular template	Deliverable	December 2024	They compare the environmental impact and travel time across different modes of travel for the five main routes from the popular Erasmus+ destinations. It included a template to build new graphs and maps.	-https://zenodo.org/records/18200406 - SET project: Mod...
3 Connectivity Reports	Deliverable	January 2025	They summarise comprehensive data on the availability of direct bus and train connections, among the top Erasmus+ destinations.	https://zenodo.org/records/17286143
Environmental sustainability in Erasmus+ student mobility: SET survey analysis	Deliverable	March 2025	It addresses the gap between students' environmental awareness and actual travel behaviour by examining the key features and reasoning behind students' transport choices for mobility.	https://zenodo.org/records/16947774
SET Green Competencies Repository	Deliverable	August 2025	It presents, in an interactive and innovative way, a comprehensive list of sixteen complementary transversal competencies that students can apply when travelling sustainably.	https://view.genially.com/667010b715e98800146f274c/interactive-content-set-green-skills-repository
Dossier for HEIs	Deliverable	May 2026	It discusses flexible institutional mechanisms that support the enhancement of green competencies and validate students' choice to travel green to/from their mobility destination.	https://zenodo.org/records/20160763
Guidelines for stakeholders on supporting green travelling	Deliverable	May 2026	They help stakeholders communicate about green travelling most effectively, focusing on relevant key messages and information tailored to the tone and scope of each actor's communication channel.	https://zenodo.org/records/20419107
Sustainable Erasmus Travel Report	Deliverable	May 2026	The goal is to incentivise students to choose sustainable travel by making the journey an enriching experience in itself.	https://zenodo.org/records/20418944
Sustainable Erasmus Journey Platform	Deliverable	March 2025	It serves as a central information hub with useful materials and resources for mobile students to organise their green journeys.	https://erasmusgeneration.org/travel-green

Sustainable Erasmus Travel Mailing List	Communication channel	Since June 2024	A Google Group for higher education practitioners, students, and policy makers to receive regular updates on SET-related calls to action and new green resources.	https://set-project.eu/#contact
Midterm dissemination event	Conference	September 2025	A fishbowl and a poster session at the 2025 EAIE Conference in Gothenburg, with the aim of expanding the project results' outreach in the biggest annual conference on international higher education in Europe.	https://set-project.eu/set-sessions-at-eaie-gothenburg-2025/
Student Mobility Summit	Conference	February 2025	Several sessions were held at this 2.5-day conference on "More mobility, less carbon footprint," hosted at the University of Barcelona.	https://set-project.eu/set-project-leads-key-sessions-at-the-student-mobility-summit-2025/
Central European Education Conference (CEEDUCON)	Conference	November 2025	Under the "Smart & Sustainable International Cooperation" thematic area, the SET consortium held a panel on "Enabling Green Mobility: Student Perspectives and University Practices".	https://set-project.eu/presenting-the-set-results-at-ceeducon-2025/
2 Green Storyteller webinars	Online events	November 2025 & May 2026	Two interactive webinars featuring 16 students who chose eco-friendly travel options for their Erasmus+ destinations. The recordings are available on the EUF's YouTube channel.	- Green Storyteller Webinar 1 - Green Storyteller Webinar 2
Final dissemination event	Conference	April 2026	At the Erasmus Generation Meeting, we attracted 149 participants who directly engaged in various sessions and activities.	https://set-project.eu/set-closing-event-at-the-2026-erasmus-generation-meeting/
Lunchtime Webinar on the SET project	Online event	May 2026	Hosted by the SALTO Green Resource Centre to present the project's objectives, methodology, and key results.	Lunchtime Webi...

To conclude, our research and on-the-ground experience revealed two main areas for improvement. Firstly, there is strong added value in systematising and streamlining training and **capacity-building opportunities for both students and staff members to continue promoting green travel options**, enrich our knowledge of its challenges and benefits, sustain knowledge transfer, and contribute to behaviour change in the long run. Secondly, awareness-raising campaigns that leverage targeted and consistent messaging, peer influence, and innovative tools should embrace and explicitly **champion the potential of green travel to foster transversal competencies**.

Introduction

The transition to sustainable mobility has become more than a vague promise; it is a strategic priority for the European Union, particularly in the fields of higher education and international cooperation. As one of the EU's flagship programmes, Erasmus+ has played an undeniable role in fostering European values and connecting millions of students and staff members across Europe with learning opportunities that have a lifelong impact. However, the programme's reliance on international mobility raised significant environmental concerns, particularly regarding greenhouse gas emissions generated through air travel. Against this backdrop, promoting and advocating for more sustainable forms of travel has become essential in aligning Erasmus+ with broader climate policy goals and objectives.

The [Sustainable Erasmus+ Travel \(SET\) project](#) was launched to leave a mark on this transition towards green travel. Funded as a KA2 project by the Erasmus+ programme, SET began in February 2024 and concluded in 2026, reaching the overarching objectives of encouraging and facilitating greener practices among students and staff. It is coordinated by the European University Foundation (EUF), in close collaboration with the University of Porto, the University of Zurich, Charles University, the Erasmus Student Network, and two associated partners, Erasmus by Train and Generation Climate Europe. The consortium brought together **experienced partners committed to advancing environmental sustainability in student mobility, viewing this transition as a paradigm shift rather than an incremental change**. Through research, engagement, communication campaigns, and innovative tools, the project sought to address barriers that prevent students and staff from choosing sustainable modes of transport and to promote the educational value of green travel, viewing it as a transformative experience in itself.

In line with these goals, the SET project aimed to better understand mobility behaviours and perceptions on sustainable travel, improve access to information and resources to support green journeys, raise awareness of the environmental impact of mobility choices, highlight and recognise the transversal competencies fostered through sustainable travel, and propose more robust institutional policies in support of greener Erasmus+ mobility. Dedicated to these objectives, the consortium developed a **range of publicly accessible outputs**: survey analyses, connectivity reports, awareness campaign materials, communication guidelines for stakeholders, a green competencies repository, and, lastly, institutional recommendations.

The document at hand builds on evidence, findings, and experiences gathered throughout the project. The key objective of these policy recommendations is to formulate concrete, actionable recommendations for European institutions, national agencies, higher education institutions, mobility practitioners, and students. With a focus on **structural and behavioural dimensions of green mobility**,

particular attention is paid to improving access to sustainable modes of travel, recognising the inherent value of green competencies, and strengthening institutional commitments.

European and national policymakers, notably the European Commission and Erasmus+ National Agencies, as well as Higher Education Institutions, International Relations Offices, and other relevant stakeholders working on mobility and sustainability, are the intended audiences of this report. At the same time, the report may serve as a useful resource for students and staff members interested in understanding sustainable travel within Erasmus+, therefore covering a broad base of actors.

The methodology underpinning this report combines desk research, policy analysis, and empirical findings collected during the project. As such, the recommendations are informed by several key outputs, including a large-scale student survey on environmental sustainability in Erasmus+, a connectivity report examining rail and bus options and durations across popular Erasmus+ destinations, validation work on green transversal competencies, and feedback collected from students, partners, and institutions. The analytical dimension of this report is reinforced by drawing upon existing European policy frameworks, academic literature, statistics, and reports from organisations working on sustainable mobility.

This document is structured in several sections. Following this introduction, key recommendations on green travel and sustainable mobility practices are presented. Thereafter, the recognition and validity of green transversal competencies are discussed, building on the previous section. A third section outlines transversal recommendations relevant to both mobility support measures and competency development, including awareness-raising, monitoring, and stakeholder engagement. Subsequently, the recommendations conclude with a broader call for better-connected rail infrastructure and more integrated European transport systems as essential for enabling conditions for green travel. The final chapter summarises the main findings and recommendations and reflects on the future of sustainable Erasmus+ mobility within the wider climate transition in Europe.

Recommendations for green travel

To guarantee clarity and cohesion, the SET project has adopted the definition for “green travel” from the [Erasmus+ programme guide](#): “Travel that uses low emissions means of transport for at least half of the round trip, such as bus, train, bike, or car-pooling. Traveling by boat will be considered as green travel if combined with other low-emissions means of transport.” In other words, green travel commonly refers to ground and public transport, or a substitute for flying. The consortium welcomes the addition of boats as an eligible mode of transportation, which can effectively establish green travel as more inclusive and accessible to students, especially those in peripheral regions, islands or coastal areas, albeit only for part of their trip.

a) Gaps identified

Historically, [in the EU](#), the transportation sector represents nearly one-fourth of the bloc’s GHG emissions and is even “the only remaining economic sector where emissions are still above 1990 levels.” According to the [European Environmental Agency](#), international aviation and maritime travel have traditionally been the biggest polluters. Conversely, rail transport has been documented as significantly lower-emitting, and its emissions have shown a slow, yet continuous downward trend since 1990. This contrast is more strikingly depicted in the graph below, with trains accounting for nearly 1/5 and buses half of the GHG emissions produced by flying.

Average GHG emissions by motorised mode of passenger transport, EU-27, 2014-2018

Source: European Environment Agency.

When considering the carbon footprint of the Erasmus+ programme, specifically for student mobility in higher education, planes remain by far the most popular means of transport. According to the latest [ESNsurvey](#), slightly more than 70% of respondents opted for air travel to reach and return from their mobility destinations. Interestingly, for trips taken during the mobility period, flying is the third most popular option (less than 9%), with buses and trains combined accounting for approximately two-thirds of travel. This contradicts the commonplace notion of “hypermobility,” whereby students prefer quick, cheap flights for leisure trips during their exchange abroad. In the [SET student survey](#), answered by more than 2,000 students, 52% of respondents used a sustainable mode of transport for their mobility, and 70% described it as a “positive” experience, which is very encouraging.

Source: Dias, R.

b) Recommended actions

In order to strengthen sustainability in the Erasmus+ programme, we need to address the biggest polluting factor, flying, and the conventional attitudes around it. Several changes can be carried out with a two-fold aim: a) to increase the uptake of the green travel support (formerly known as the “green top-up”) and reach its full potential, notably for routes with a feasible green alternative, and b) to lower travel-related emissions by adopting and mainstreaming eco-friendly habits.

To begin with, **concise, accessible, and up-to-date information on the eligibility criteria for green travel is a key success factor.** Our [research findings](#) demonstrated the need for “earlier, clearer, and more detailed guidance, particularly on eligibility for green funding, sustainable travel options, and practical booking tips”. In addition, when asked whether students were informed about the green travel allowance, slightly fewer than 20% were either uninformed or unaware. This information about the criteria and eligibility for the green travel support is currently widely reaching students through official websites, platforms, and university staff (Erasmus+ coordinators and related roles), highlighting the central role of HEIs in promoting awareness of sustainable travel. By extension, the role of the EC and NAs would be not only to encourage Universities to provide these support measures but also to reinforce consistent, cohesive guidelines to make green travel as accessible, equitable, and feasible as possible. In short, if students are not aware of the possibility and the financial incentives to travel sustainably, they are less likely to do so.

Secondly, students called for **further assistance in making logistical arrangements, bookings, and planning green routes**. Such administrative barriers and a lack of practical skills typically prevent many students from scheduling, reserving, and completing an international green trip, which is often perceived as more complex than flying, as evidenced by an [academic article](#) from the Erasmus Goes Green consortium. In another [Nuffic](#) report, it was reiterated that opting for plane tickets was perceived as the “easiest to organise,” and that “70% of the students surveyed would like to receive advice during their time away and help with booking sustainable travel.” This need highlights untapped opportunities for higher education stakeholders to support students in making well-informed, eco-friendly decisions. A more recent [study](#) revealed the actual disparities in visibility, transparency, pricing, and booking processes between rail and air companies for international travel.

Thankfully, there are initiatives that can help overcome some of these challenges, for instance, the [Interrail Pass for Erasmus+](#) and [Go2Rail](#). The former allows students (and staff) to easily arrange their travel in a single app, with unlimited travel on participating networks for 4 or 6 days within a 6-month period. The latter helps exchange students travel together by train through its smart grouping bot, take advantage of discounts, and make the journey more informative and social.

Another recommendation is to enrich the universities' responsibilities laid out in the [ECHE](#). Currently, they merely sign up to “promoting environmentally friendly practices in all activities related to the Programme.” We call for the **ECHE to strengthen the commitments of HEIS to environmental sustainability by explicitly mentioning and promoting green travel**, similar to what is described in the Erasmus+ Guide: “Erasmus+, with mobility at its core, should strive for carbon-neutrality by promoting sustainable transport modes and more environmentally responsible behavior.” This intervention will place travelling at the centre of the discussion and advance institutional accountability to help make green mobility the norm and align with European policies and programme priorities. As a

second step, it could lead to better monitoring of the implementation of these practices by HEIs, through their respective National Agencies, to ensure that legal responsibilities align with real-life actions.

Furthermore, **information and awareness efforts should focus on promoting alternative green routes, practical tips, and useful resources for booking a green journey.** (SET) The Erasmus Generation Portal, owned and managed by ESN International, has a dedicated [Travel Green subpage](#) with tailored resources, including green guides for incoming students on living responsibly on campus and in the host city. Alternatively, the SET project produced [10 fact sheets](#) on the environmental impact and travel time on different travel modes for the five main routes taken from the popular Erasmus+ destinations, a [modular template](#) to create your own fact sheet for your university's key destinations and build upon existing graphs and maps, and [three connectivity reports](#) showing connections and possible stopovers from Porto, Prague, and Zurich.

Source: SET project consortium.

c) Impact

A structural, high-level shift is needed to bridge the information-action gap and deliver informed decision-making. Centralised, tailored, proactive, and actionable materials can significantly enable more students not only to consider but also to choose low-carbon means of transport. Over time, we can expect the increased normalisation and popularity of green travel, moving from incentive-based exceptions to the default option.

Recommendations for green competencies

The SET consortium conducted extensive desk research and validation rounds in order to identify the **transversal and complementary competencies that students who travel sustainably to/from their destinations can foster**. Competencies are understood as an umbrella term encompassing knowledge, skills, and attitudes, and they are transversal because they are lifelong, interdisciplinary, and holistic. (Council Recommendations) The competencies that might be fostered are in alphabetical order: adaptability/flexibility, adopting ways to reduce the negative impact of consumption, critical thinking, curiosity, emotional regulation, environmental values, European values, evaluating data, information and digital content, evaluating the environmental impact of personal behaviour, individual initiative, intercultural awareness, interpersonal communication, online search, planning, responsibility, and self-motivation (See Annex for the full list of the 16 competencies and their definitions). Preparing for and actually experiencing green travel fits the description of an informal learning opportunity, “which is not organised or structured in terms of objectives, time or learning support; it may be unintentional from the learner’s perspective,” according to the [Erasmus+ Programme Guide](#).

a) Gaps identified

The enhancement of such competencies is a central argument in favour of green travel, which is beneficial not only for its lower carbon footprint but also for personal growth and self-realisation. The mainstreaming of this notion can help **change the cultural narrative around slow and green travel by highlighting its added value**. Ultimately, this mindset shift can help bridge the gap between awareness and action, as documented in the [Erasmus Goes Green project](#) and the [ESNsurvey](#).

Poster presentation of the Green Competencies Repository at EAIE Toulouse in 2024.

Source: SET project consortium.

b) Recommended actions

The recognition of informal and non-formal learning aligns with **several European policies that champion the validation of knowledge, practical and soft skills, values and attitudes acquired through various methods**, as explored by the [European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training](#). Lifelong learning and the complementarity of the three learning settings (formal, informal and non-formal) have been acknowledged in the European Skills Agenda, the European Area of Education, the reinforced Youth Guarantee, and the European Social Pillar Action Plan. Concrete guidelines have been outlined in the [2012 Council Recommendation on validation of non-formal and informal learning](#), which substantiate informal learning as manifesting in daily and life experiences, including “intercultural skills acquired during a stay in another country”. Even more so, since its establishment in 1989, the European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS) “awards credits for formal learning based on learning outcomes and student workload, and also facilitates the award by higher education institutions of credits based on learning outcomes for non-formal and informal learning experiences.”

The [Erasmus+ Student Charter](#) provides an appropriate context for introducing this concept by outlining both the rights and responsibilities of mobile students. We propose including a statement under the **entitlements after the mobility period, recognising green travel as an educative and transformative experience** that can foster the development of transversal and intercultural competencies. Moreover, we suggest a similar addition to the ECHE, as universities are the key actors in validating these competencies, on a more or less formal basis. In the [Dossier on Recognition Mechanisms of Sustainable Travel for European Higher Education Institutions](#), we encourage them to reflect on whether they can implement a flexible, credible, and student-centred approach, depending on their institutional context, such as through a self-assessment questionnaire, the issuance of certificates and digital credentials, the Diploma Supplement, or even academic recognition through ECTS.

c) Impact

A number of intended and positive effects might result from the aforementioned recommendations. On the one hand, we can anticipate an increased uptake of green travel support because students can see the full potential of this experience and recognise the journey as educational. At the same time, graduates’ employability prospects can be strengthened in an ever-changing labour market, where fundamental competencies (ranging from adaptability and curiosity to communication and environmental awareness, and more) are necessary for all workers. This is thanks to the **overlap between the competencies fostered in green travel and those most needed in the future**, regardless of field of work, sector, or discipline, as we explored in [desk research](#). Lastly, these efforts strive to **improve the quality and satisfaction of the mobility experience**, thanks to students’ comprehensive acknowledgement and ownership of the diverse and complementary competencies they have cultivated throughout their academic exchange period.

Transversal recommendations

There are three main intersecting measures that apply to both green travel and green competencies. Firstly, **data collection, monitoring, and impact assessment** are paramount for adequately testing the effectiveness of any intervention. Regular feedback and evaluation by the affected stakeholders, first and foremost, mobile students, as well as staff members working on Erasmus+ student mobility, are essential, depending on the processes applied, to assess whether the predetermined objectives are being met and to identify areas for improvement.

Secondly, the [SET student survey](#) revealed that **sharing stories from previous students who travelled sustainably** could play a decisive role in shifting perceptions and motivating future cohorts. There are three main objectives to be achieved through this type of intervention: a) mitigating risk perception, b) practical knowledge transfer, and c) fostering community and belonging. In practice, the collection and dissemination of these testimonials can be carried out at the local, national, and European levels. For example, students are invited to complete their post-mobility survey and can explicitly mention their green journey, the lessons learned, and tips for other students. In parallel, ESN is currently featuring real success stories on their [Testimonials](#) and [Blog](#) pages from the two rounds of the SET awareness campaign in 2025. New additions can be made for future green travellers who directly reach students from all participating countries. This peer-to-peer knowledge sharing has the potential to showcase the multiple benefits of green travel, make it seem more attainable, and inspire others.

There is also an **undeniable potential for mobile staff members, whether academic or administrative, to become ambassadors for green travel**. Their own green travel experiences can further inspire students and have a positive spillover effect on their colleagues and other actors within the HEI ecosystem, where we can uplift one another and demonstrate the power of collective action. The SET team is proud to have travelled to most international meetings and conferences primarily by ground transport, for instance, when two staff members from CU and UZH travelled to the [EAIE Conference in Gothenburg in 2025](#). The SALTO (Support, Advanced Learning and Training Opportunities) Green resource centre on ecological transition in all sectors of the Erasmus+ and European Solidarity Corps programmes [posted an audio testimonial and a one-pager](#) on staff mobility.

Visuals for the green staff travel testimonies, 2025.

Source: EUF.

Thirdly, higher education stakeholders can collectively **defend better ground travel infrastructure and cross-border connections**. According to [Greenpeace](#), among the main European cities, there are six times as many direct flights connecting them as there are by train. Even more so, “Direct train connections in Europe could be more than tripled using existing track infrastructure.” [Eurostat](#) also reveals the lack of homogeneity in the railway networks across the continent, with some countries exhibiting high density and availability, like Belgium, Germany, and Czechia (all of which are in Central and Western Europe), compared to less accessible destinations, such as the Baltic states, Portugal, Greece, and Finland. Research carried out by [ESN](#) and the [SET consortium](#) has highlighted the need to upgrade national and international infrastructure, especially in the rail sector, so as to make ground travel faster, easier, and safer for everyone.

A call for better-connected rail infrastructure

The transition to a green Erasmus+ programme cannot be achieved through incentives and behavioural change alone; it needs **better-connected, affordable, safe, and punctual rail infrastructure**. The current landscape raises serious structural limitations that virtually undermine the European project, its decades-long ambition for better interconnectedness and cohesion, and even the free movement of people, goods, and services. Despite increasing willingness to travel green and policy commitments to environmental sustainability and carbon neutrality, students' choices are largely shaped by price, speed, and availability, which often favour flying, the most polluting means of transport.

2021 marked the [European Year of Rail](#), a symbolic and strategic initiative aimed at reviving and expanding night train connections. An [Action Plan](#) was published in December 2021 to “boost long-distance and cross-border passenger rail services,” covering a range of recommendations, such as, but not limited to, modernising and leveraging existing rail infrastructure, simplifying ticketing, and “making sustainable transport modes an attractive option for young people”.

Similarly, the [Green Rail Investment Platform](#), launched in 2021, accelerated the sector's recovery from the COVID-19 pandemic and contributed to the Union's decarbonisation efforts. On the other hand, the expansion of [European Sleeper](#) routes in recent years has amplified the demand for more direct lines. As of March 2026, Paris and Berlin, two major Erasmus+ hubs for student mobility, are again directly connected via night train, whereas in September of the same year, a new line will link Brussels, Cologne, Zurich, and Milan. In addition, the [European Sleeper now connects Brussels to Prague](#) via Amsterdam and Berlin. In late 2025, it was also announced that, as of April 2026, a new direct train would run between Basel, Copenhagen, and Malmö, among other cities. However, the line was later [cancelled](#) because the Swiss parliament did not approve funding for it. This could have significantly favoured green travel to/from Scandinavia and Central Europe.

The [2025 plan to revive the trans-European transport network \(TEN-T\)](#) further pushes the envelope to offer high-speed rail services across the European continent. It prioritised faster, direct, and more convenient cross-border and long-distance train alternatives through 804 projects funded by the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF). Once completed, thousands of Erasmus+ students and staff can benefit from harmonised, coherent, and high-speed rail journeys. This is a step in the right direction, considering that a majority of Europe's train infrastructure today remains fragmented, unevenly developed, and insufficiently integrated; there is great room for improvement, particularly in Mediterranean and Eastern European Countries.

Passenger Package

Simplifying EU-wide travel booking

One journey, one ticket, full rights

Passengers will be able to **find, compare** and **combine** services from different rail operators in **one transaction** on a platform of their choice, including for **cross-border journeys**.

Plan, book, go.

Stronger passenger rights

Rail passengers with a **single ticket** will benefit from **assistance, rerouting, reimbursement and compensation** in case of missed connections during their rail journeys.

Fair competition

New obligations for ticketing platforms and operators will ensure **fair access to tickets** and the **transparent presentation** of travel options.

© European Union, 2026
Reuse of this document is allowed, provided appropriate credit is given and any changes are indicated (Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license).
For any use or reproduction of elements that are not owned by the EU, permission may need to be sought directly from the respective right holders. Images: © valantsin / Barillo Images - stock.adobe.com, © European Union

The recommendations presented above – improving information sharing and practical support, strengthening institutional commitments, raising awareness of the development and recognition of green competencies – can only reach their full potential if **the railway industry, as the least emissions-intensive mode of transport, is integrated, modernised, reliable, accessible, and affordable**. Regulatory efforts to improve ticketing, interoperability, and data sharing are key success factors for reducing the complexity often associated with cross-border train journeys today.

Conclusions

The SET project has demonstrated that **greener Erasmus+ mobility is both achievable and desirable** when higher education students, institutions, and other mobility stakeholders are collectively supported through coherent policies, practical tools, and targeted by effective campaign-raising efforts. Throughout the project, research findings and on-the-ground experiences consistently showed that students are increasingly willing to adopt sustainable travel behaviours, provided that the necessary conditions (notably affordability, accessibility, reliable infrastructure and clear information) are in place.

At the same time, SET highlighted that green travel should not be understood as merely an environmental measure aimed at reducing emissions. **Sustainable mobility also represents a valuable learning experience capable of cultivating a broad range of competencies.** Recognising and validating these competencies, namely, personal development, environmental awareness, and stronger engagement with European values, can help reshape perceptions of green travel from a –for some perceived– inconvenient alternative into an enriching and meaningful component of the Erasmus+ experience.

The recommendations presented in this report, therefore, advocate a **comprehensive and systemic approach to greener mobility.** This includes improving communication and guidance for students, strengthening institutional commitments through frameworks such as the Erasmus Charter for Higher Education and the Erasmus+ Student Charter, expanding practical support for booking and organising sustainable journeys, and investing in more integrated and accessible rail infrastructure across Europe. Equally important is the need to continue collecting data, sharing success stories, and empowering both students and staff members to act as ambassadors for sustainable mobility in their communities.

Within Europe's commitments to climate change and its efforts to create a more sustainable and resilient future, **Erasmus+ has the potential to become an environmental leadership programme.** The SET project contributes to this ambition by providing evidence-based recommendations, innovative resources, and practical pathways for change. However, achieving a genuine modal shift towards green travel will require sustained political commitment, long-term investment, and close cooperation among a range of actors to effect change. Ultimately, rethinking sustainable travel as the norm within Erasmus+ is not only about reducing carbon emissions but also about reimagining mobility as a more conscious, intentional, and transformative experience that can meaningfully contribute to Europe's climate transition goals.

References

Cedefop. (2026). *An EU reference framework for lifelong guidance. 18 guidelines for policy and systems development*. Cedefop reference series; 128. Publications Office of the European Union. DOI: 10.2801/8255414 <https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/en/publications/3098>

Dias, R. (2024). *ESNsurvey - 15th Edition: Making Quality Mobility a Reality for All*. <https://esn.org/esnsurvey>

Diekmann, A., & Karaiskos, G. (2022). *Research on the habits of Erasmus students*. Green Erasmus Partnership. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10654122>

European Commission. (2021). *Action Plan on long-distance and cross-border passenger rail*. https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-modes/rail/action-plan-long-distance-and-cross-border-passenger-rail_en

European Commission. (n.d.). *Erasmus Charter for Higher Education (ECHE)*. <https://erasmus-plus.ec.europa.eu/programme-guide/part-b/three-key-actions/learning-mobility-individuals/erasmus-charter-for-higher-education>

European Commission. (2026a). *Erasmus+ Programme Guide 2026*. <https://erasmus-plus.ec.europa.eu/programme-guide/erasmusplus-programme-guide>

European Commission. (n.d.). *Erasmus+ Student Charter*. <https://erasmus-plus.ec.europa.eu/resources-and-tools/erasmus-student-charter>

European Commission. (2026b). *One journey, one ticket, full rights: Commission simplifies Europe-wide travel booking and train travel* [Press release]. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_26_1056

European Environment Agency. (2025). *Transport and environment report*. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/topics/in-depth/transport>

European Sleeper. (n.d.). *Routes and connections*. <https://www.europeansleeper.eu>

European University Foundation. (2025). *Green skills and the future of employability: Aligning higher education with labour market demands*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16947420>

Eurostat. (n.d.). *Characteristics of the railway network in Europe*. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Railway_transport_statistics_-_infrastructure

Gabrielczak, P., & Sokołowicz, M. E. (2024). *Is Erasmus going green? The carbon footprint of European academic mobility and the sustainability policies of European universities*. <https://doi.org/10.18778/1231-1952.31.1.03>

Greenpeace. (2024). *Connection failed: Europe's missing train links*. <https://www.greenpeace.org/eu-unit/issues/nature-food/47189/connection-failed>

Greenpeace. (2025). *Flying cheap, paying dear: How airlines undercut rail and fuel the climate crisis*. <https://www.greenpeace.org/eu-unit/>

Nuffic. (2022). *Train or plane: A study of options and opportunities for sustainable internationalisation*. <https://www.nuffic.nl>

Sustainable Erasmus+ Travel (SET) Project / European University Foundation. (2025). *Environmental sustainability in Erasmus+ student mobility: SET survey analysis*. <https://zenodo.org/records/16947774>

Sustainable Erasmus+ Travel (SET) Project / European University Foundation. (2026a). *Dossier on recognition mechanisms of sustainable travel for European higher education institutions*. <https://zenodo.org/records/20160763>

Sustainable Erasmus+ Travel (SET) Project / European University Foundation. (2026b). *Ready, SET, Green Travel – Communication Campaign Report*. <https://zenodo.org/records/20418944>

Sustainable Erasmus+ Travel (SET) Project / European University Foundation. (2026c). *Supporting Green Travelling in Student Mobility – Guidelines for Stakeholders*. <https://zenodo.org/records/20419107>

Transport & Environment. (2026). *Modernising the EU's rail ticketing regulation*. <https://www.transportenvironment.org/articles/modernising-the-eus-rail-ticketing-regulation>

University of Versailles-Saint-Quentin-en-Yvelines, University of Lodz, & Lapland University of Applied Sciences. (2021). *Assessment of the transport-related carbon footprint of the Erasmus+ programme*. Erasmus Goes Green. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10696704>

CLICK HERE TO ACCESS THE INTERACTIVE REPOSITORY

UNESCO pillar	N.	Green competence	Description	Source
Learning to be = personal and family wellbeing / to develop one's personality and be able to act with ever greater autonomy, judgement and personal responsibility. In that connection, education must not disregard any aspect of a person's potential: memory, reasoning, aesthetic sense, physical capacities and communication skills.	1	Emotional regulation	To recognise and regulate your mental and emotional state. Even though green travel can be a very social experience, it also includes moments of solitude and independence, which in turn provide an opportunity for self-reflection and consciousness. Even more so, this competence reflects the ability to cope calmly, patiently and positively against stressful and unexpected scenarios, such as in the case of delays, changes to initial plans, lack of comfort, unforeseen situations (e.g., pickpockets, extra costs, loss of luggage), and feeling lost and in unfamiliar places.	LifeComp
	2	Self-motivation	To initiate and maintain goal-driven behaviours, be self-disciplined, and challenge yourself. In some cases, sustainable travel is a more complex and demanding process to undertake, which shows commitment and courage. It can also include maintaining a positive attitude during a longer, more adventurous journey.	LifeComp
	3	Planning	To be self-reliant, take decisions, undertake responsibility, and manage your time efficiently. Sustainable travel, especially when solo, requires a lot of prior planning and organisation, for example when booking tickets with different companies, scheduling layovers/waiting time, arranging luggage, mapping train/bus connections.	WEE
	4	Responsibility	To reliably fulfil obligations with integrity and proactiveness. Students are more inclined to act proactively and responsibly, ask for and evaluate feedback, practice self-control, and be overcome with a profound and lasting feeling of pride due to their choice to travel sustainably.	OECD
	5	Curiosity	To enjoy a curious and inquisitive attitude towards new experiences and situations. Sustainable travel is not the norm; students who embark on a green journey are interested in a different and unique experience.	Erasmus Skills
	6	Environmental values	To evaluate the level of agreement between human actions at an individual or societal level and environmentalism. Evidently, students who choose to travel sustainably for their mobility are deeply concerned about the environment and want to uphold these values in practice in a meaningful and impactful way.	GreenComp
	7	Interpersonal communication	To effectively externalise and interpret information through verbal and non-verbal channels, and to possess active and empathetic listening skills. Green travel invites students to use their communication and collaborative skills, in their native or a foreign tongue, for example to ask for advice or information from a help desk, a staff on board, or a fellow traveler.	Erasmus Skills
Learning to be together = social cohesion, intercultural and international cooperation and peace / developing an understanding of other people and an appreciation of interdependence - carrying out joint projects and learning to manage conflicts - in a spirit of respect for the values of pluralism, mutual understanding and peace	8	Intercultural awareness	To have an understanding of the characteristics of your own and other cultures. Students who choose to travel sustainably can not only be more closely exposed to different people and cultures, but they also have an opportunity to get immersed in new environments and engage with the local community, especially if they stop along the way. This experience can put them in direct contact with other cultures, traditions, practices, and mentalities. A positive consequence is the greater respect for diversity.	Erasmus Skills
	9	European values	To see yourself as part of the European identity (solely or in addition/parallel to other identity groups). The act of literally crossing borders by land brings students in touch with their European identity, for example when they travel visa and passport-free between countries that form part of the Schengen Area. They begin to appreciate and materialise the meaning of the freedom of movement.	Erasmus Skills
Learning to do = Engagement in productive work and recreation / to acquire not only an occupational skill but also, more broadly, the competence to deal with many situations and work in teams, also in the context of young peoples' various social and work experiences which may be informal, as a result of the local or national context, or formal, involving courses, alternating study and work	10	Individual initiative	To recognise the personal potential to proactively promote sustainability. Students fully realise that green travel is an option for them, they feel certain and confident in pursuing it, and are actually willing to act according to this conviction.	GreenComp
	11	Online search	To search for and sort online data, information and content. Especially in the preparation phase of the journey, students resort to online platforms, apps, and websites to research information (e.g., connections, stops, layovers, documentation). They also stay updated during the trip following the latest news and receiving notifications on their phone/via email.	DigComp
	12	Evaluating data, information and digital content	Students assess the validity/credibility of information online, compare their options, as well as try to identify greenwashing practices. Students explore new/innovative ways to search for and exchange information, e.g. via online forums, apps and platforms that are dedicated to green travel.	DigComp
Learning to know = respecting and searching for knowledge and wisdom / combining a sufficiently broad general knowledge with the opportunity to work in depth on a small number of subjects. This also means learning to learn, so as to benefit from the opportunities education provides throughout life.	13	Critical thinking	To be able to solve problems and structure arguments based on analytical skills and logical reasoning. This is a fundamental tool that enables students to evaluate the information at hand, make an informed judgment, open their horizons and challenge preconceived notions around green travel and Erasmus+, all of which ultimately empowers them.	LifeComp
Learning to transform oneself and society = active citizenship, futures thinking, responsible lifestyles, sharing of resources and adaptability	14	Adaptability/Flexibility	To successfully and calmly answer and react to new situations and ambiguity. Sustainable travel tends to be less straightforward and smoother than originally expected. This experience enables students to learn how to respond appropriately to new circumstances and resolve unforeseen problems. In a realistic scenario of adversity, creative thinking can help a student come up with a solution to overcome a problem during their journey; for example, when a train is cancelled, they can figure out an alternative route that could be even more convenient than the original plan.	Erasmus Skills
	15	Evaluate environmental impact of personal behaviour	To critically reflect on the different dimensions of your lifestyle and its impact on the natural environment. Self-evident in the case of green travel that has a lower environmental impact than flying; potential of spillover effect in other aspects of lifestyle, such as food, clothing, waste.	ESCO
	16	Adopt ways to reduce the negative impact of consumption	To take responsible and eco-conscious decisions that strive to decrease the harmful environmental impact of your consumption patterns. Students are agents of positive change and actively contribute to changing the narrative around traveling by 'stepping up' and 'practicing what they preach'.	ESCO